

Local Wisdom-Based Environmental Communication in the Preservation of Marena Customary Forests in Enrekang Regency, Indonesia

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Abstract:

This study analyses the role of local wisdom-based environmental communication in the preservation of the Marena Customary Forest in Enrekang Regency, South Sulawesi, Indonesia. Using a qualitative case study approach, data were collected from non-participant observation, in-depth interviews with 10 traditional leaders (Batu Ariri), community leaders, and conservationists, as well as analysis of traditional documents (Eda wa'ding). The results reveal three key communication patterns: (1) Ritual (offering manuk-lappa lappa to ask for ancestral permission before agricultural activities); (2) Normative (customary prohibitions such as logging/forest burning); and (3) Layered sanctions (gerek tedong pujan—slaughtering a black buffalo for serious violations). Participatory mechanisms such as Si Ottoman Upa (egalitarian decision-making with knees touching) and traditional "forest police" surveillance reinforce the system's effectiveness. This local wisdom successfully combines spiritual, ecological, and social aspects, as evidenced by sustainable practices (wood replacement: planting two seedlings per tree used). The challenges of modernisation are overcome through adaptive collaboration with the government (e.g., coffee seedling project). It is concluded that the Marena communication model offers a framework for preservation that is resistant to changing times, with recommendations for the digital codification of customary rules and their integration into national conservation policies.

Keywords: Environmental Communication, Marena Customary Forest, Local Wisdom, Enrekang.

INTRODUCTION

As a megabiodiversity country, Indonesia faces complex challenges in balancing the use of natural resources with ecosystem conservation. Amidst the pressures of development and modernisation, indigenous peoples with their traditional knowledge systems have emerged as key actors in sustainable conservation practices. Customary forests, which occupy a strategic position in biodiversity conservation, not only function

as ecological buffers but also as spaces for the preservation of local cultures that have been tested over centuries.

The Marena Indigenous Forest in Enrekang Regency, South Sulawesi, represents a unique model of forest management based on local wisdom that has survived for hundreds of years. This 155-hectare area, part of a total indigenous area of 676.32 hectares, was officially recognised by the government in 2016 as an indigenous forest. The success of the Marena Indigenous community in preserving their forest has attracted attention due to the effectiveness of their traditional communication system, which still functions today, even in the modern technological era.

Environmental communication in the context of indigenous communities has distinctive characteristics compared to modern environmental communication. Berkes (2017) Explains that traditional environmental communication tends to be participatory, holistic, and integrated with the cultural value system of the community. In the Marena Customary Forest, environmental communication goes beyond the mere transfer of information—it involves all dimensions of the community's social, cultural, and spiritual life. This communication system is managed by the Sia Nenek customary institution, which consists of four customary leaders (Batu Ariri) without a structural hierarchy, adhering to the egalitarian principle of "*Mesa soe mesa tengka pada tallan pada lindang*" (one step, one movement, sharing both hardship and joy).

An interesting phenomenon to study is how the Marena customary communication system integrates rituals, norms, and traditional sanctions into environmental conservation practices. Rituals such as the manuk-lappa lappa offering before agricultural activities, customary prohibitions on logging and forest burning, and layered sanctions such as gerak tedong pujak (cutting down a black buffalo) for serious violations, form a complex but compelling communication ecosystem that maintains forest sustainability.

Although the role of environmental communication in conservation has been widely studied, research that explores explicitly patterns of communication based on local wisdom in the context of indigenous communities in Indonesia is still limited. Previous studies, such as Widiaksono (Widhiaksono, 2009) focused more on efforts to maintain forest sustainability with local wisdom in general, while Herutomo & Istiyanto (2021) Examined environmental communication in forest sustainability development without comprehensively exploring the mechanisms of traditional communication. This gap in the literature opens up opportunities to explore in depth how traditional communication systems function as instruments for preserving ecosystems that are resistant to change over time.

METHOD

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach with a *case study* method, which is a type of qualitative approach that explores real-life, limited, diverse systems (various cases), through detailed and in-depth data collection involving various sources of information or multiple sources of information, such as observations, interviews, audiovisual materials, documents, and various reports (Creswell, 2014). This research is classified as *field research*, which aims to examine a social unit in depth in order to produce a well-organised and comprehensive picture. A sociological approach was applied as the theoretical basis in this study, namely an approach using social sciences that study communal life in society and investigate the bonds between humans that

govern their lives (Soekanto, 2002). This approach was chosen because the researchers interacted extensively with the community of Enrekang Regency, and in collecting data, the researchers used instruments that included questions covering social aspects that had to be answered by the respondents.

The research location was set in Pekalobean Marena Village, Enrekang Regency, South Sulawesi. This place was chosen because the village has a customary forest that is well preserved and maintained, and is the centre of customary forest management that has been recognised by the government since 2016, and still maintains traditional communication practices in ecosystem preservation. The research was conducted over three months, from June 2024 to August 2024, with the following stages: June 2024 for preliminary studies and licensing, July 2024 for primary data collection through observation and in-depth interviews, and August 2024 for supplementary data collection, data verification, and preliminary analysis.

The data sources in this study refer to where the research data can be obtained. This qualitative study was determined purposively, which is a technique of collecting data sources based on the rational consideration that informants have the authority and competence to provide information or data in accordance with the researcher's expectations. (Sugiyono, 2016). The criteria for informants used in this study were the people of Pekalobean, Enrekang Regency. The research data sources were divided into two types. First, primary data sources, namely parties considered to be most knowledgeable about issues related to the research being conducted (Arikunto, 2013), including traditional leaders (Batu Ariri), religious leaders, village officials, and the local community. Second, secondary data sources, which are supporting data to facilitate the writing of this scientific paper in accordance with the research object, in the form of books, archives, official documents on the designation of customary forests, ritual records, archives of traditional sanctions, notes related to the research, various journals, newspapers, or articles relevant to this research. In addition, the researcher also used library research as additional material in this study by utilising the internet to help find unanswered questions and supplement the interview results so that all questions related to the problem could be adequately answered.

Data collection was carried out using three primary methods. First, observation was one of the steps in obtaining data, whereby researchers could see, hear, and feel the conditions in the field of research directly. The type of observation used was non-participatory observation, meaning that researchers were not directly involved in what was being observed, but only observed it in order to observe customary ritual activities and the application of norms in the field. (Bungin, 2007). Second, *interviews* are important in gathering information from informants. The type of interview used is both covert and overt. An open interview is conducted openly, meaning that both the interviewer and interviewee are aware of the interview process, while a closed interview occurs when the interviewee is unaware that an interview is taking place (Moleong, 2018). The interviews were conducted using open-ended questions to explore patterns of ritual communication, norms, and sanctions. Third, documentation is necessary for the completeness of research data. Documentation is a data collection technique in the form of notes, transcripts, books, letters, pictures/photos, inscriptions, and others (Sugiyono, 2016). This is applied to collect cultural artefacts such as written customary rules (*Eda wa'ding*), photos of sacred sites, and records of customary deliberations.

Research instruments are tools used to measure and collect quantitative and qualitative information. According to Arikunto (Arikunto, 2013) Research instruments are tools selected and used by researchers in carrying out their activities to collect data, so that these activities become systematic and easier. Research instruments are all the tools used to obtain, manage, and interpret information from respondents using the same measurement pattern, which plays a vital role in determining the quality of a study. The use of appropriate instruments has a significant impact on the quality of research results, and the measure of research success also depends on the research instruments used. The main research instrument is the researcher himself, who acts as a direct data collector. Field research, which includes observation and interviews, requires several supporting instruments, namely interview guidelines with a list of questions that have been prepared in advance and validated, field notes, audio recorders, documentation cameras, and writing tools such as notebooks, pens, or cell phones to collect various information that is processed and organised systematically while obtaining more accurate data.

The data processing technique referred to is data that is obtained, collected, processed, and utilised in such a way using descriptive methods, namely describing the meaning of data or phenomena that researchers can capture by presenting evidence. Data analysis in qualitative research is an activity that is carried out continuously throughout the research, from data collection to the writing of the report (Miles et al., 2014). Data analysis is an effort to systematically organise and arrange records of interviews, observations, documentation, and other sources to enhance the researcher's understanding of the case being studied and to provide findings for others. During the research process, researchers must continuously analyze all data, whether in the form of field notes, capturing important points from interview results, and trying to focus the research by organizing the data into categories, breaking it down into units, and selecting what is important and what will be studied so that when concluding, they are easy to understand by oneself and others.

DISCUSSION

1. Marena Customary Forest

The Marena Customary Forest has a long history that began with a reforestation program under the auspices of the Forestry Service in 1975. At that time, the Marena customary forest area was under the control of the Forestry Service and was planted with pine trees. Mardan, the Head of Marena Village, explained the situation at that time, saying that the community was only told to plant pine trees without any explicit rules. After the trees grew large, the community was confused about how to use them. The year 2016 was an important milestone when the land rights of the Marena community were fully controlled for use as long as it did not conflict with applicable cultural norms. The total area of Marena Customary Territory is 676.34 hectares, with 155 hectares of forest. Data from AMAN Massenrempulu's participatory mapping shows that the recognised area of Marena Customary Territory is 676.32 hectares, indicating the State's formal recognition of the existence and rights of indigenous peoples over the area.

The Marena Indigenous Community consists of two villages, namely Pekalobean Village and Singki Village, with five hamlets, namely Lando Tete, Lembong, Dale, Paropo, and Batu Rape. The indigenous institutional structure has its own uniqueness in its organisational system. The Marena Indigenous Institution is called Sia Nenek, which

consists of four traditional leaders (Batu Ariri) without a hierarchical structure or leadership. Pieter Kadang, the Marena Traditional Leader, explained the organisational philosophy that the Marena indigenous community does not recognise the concepts of younger or older siblings, but rather the unity of three principles (*periwa lolo katuoan tallu, lolo lise', na lolo baranggapa*), which indicate a collective and egalitarian leadership system. The basic principle that is upheld is "*Mesa soe Mesa Tengka Pada Tallan Pada Lindang*," which means one step, one movement, sharing both hardship and joy. This principle reflects strong communal solidarity in facing various challenges in managing customary forests.

In carrying out their activities, the four Batu Ariri are assisted by four technical officers with specific tasks. First, Sorong, who is fully responsible for all traditional rituals. Second, Sando, who is involved in traditional medicine. Third, the Guru or Imam, who acts as the prayer leader during traditional rituals and as the Imam at the mosque. Fourth, *to' mentaung*, who determines the timing of rituals and agricultural activities based on traditional knowledge of prediction. This clear division of tasks demonstrates a structured organisational system, albeit without a formal hierarchy, in which each position has complementary functions and responsibilities in preserving the forest and sustaining customary practices.

2. Environmental Communication Patterns Based on Local Wisdom

a. Ritual Communication Through Traditional Ceremonies

The Marena indigenous community's ritual communication system is integrated into agricultural practices that reflect the spiritual relationship between humans, nature, and ancestors. Before planting and harvesting crops, the community first goes to a sacred spring with offerings of chicken (*Manuk*) and lepet (*Lappa-lappa*), a traditional food made from sticky rice wrapped in coconut leaves. According to the beliefs of the Marena indigenous community, this ritual aims to ask permission from the ancestors and God Almighty for a bountiful harvest. This ritual shows that environmental communication is not only horizontal between humans, but also vertical, with a spiritual dimension that forms the foundation of natural resource management (Berkes, 2017).

Ritual communication protocols are also applied in clearing land around the Marena customary forest. This process requires landowners first to obtain permission from customary leaders, followed by a land clearing ceremony in which one of the customary leaders is invited to inspect the land. One day after the inspection, a prayer is recited on the land, asking the Creator for permission so that the cleared land will be fertile and produce abundant crops. This tiered permit system functions as a social control mechanism that ensures that all land clearing activities are carried out with ecological considerations and collective approval, rather than solely based on individual decisions that could damage the balance of the ecosystem.

b. Normative Communication Through Customary Rules

In the Marena customary area, three fundamental customary laws still apply to the management of customary forests. First, "*Eda wa'ding ala kaju ke eda na di petada*," which means "it is forbidden to take wood without asking permission." Second, "*Eda wa'ding Bela pangngala*," which means "it is forbidden to clear the forest." Third, "*Eda wa'ding sumpun pangngala*," which means it is prohibited to burn the forest. Pieter Kadang explained the implementation of these rules, saying that every violation has

clear and strict consequences. This customary prohibition system reflects normative communication that serves as a guide for community behaviour in interacting with the forest environment. These norms are not only prescriptive (what to do) but also proscriptive (what not to do), providing clear boundaries for the use of forest resources.

Normative communication also includes symbolic behavioural rules related to the sacred dimension of customary forests. In terms of dress code, people are not allowed to wear black clothes in areas with sacred springs and forests. When cooking, cooking utensils that have been used near springs cannot be used. Kasim explains that this local wisdom is a message that must be preserved and passed down to children as a characteristic of indigenous peoples. These symbolic rules serve as a communication mechanism that strengthens collective awareness of the sacredness of specific areas, as well as an indirect conservation strategy by limiting human access and activities in ecologically sensitive areas.

c. Communication of Sanctions Through the Traditional Punishment System

The penalty system for indigenous peoples who commit violations is resolved through customary law in a tiered manner according to the level of the violation. For the violation of taking wood without permission, the perpetrator will be "di pasun lan mai kampong" or expelled from the Marena Customary area. For the violation of clearing the forest, the perpetrator will be "*eda na di bengan wai dipakkeguna jo baraba or uma*", or denied water for their gardens or rice fields. For the most serious offence of burning the forest, the perpetrator must perform "gerek tedong pujak" or slaughter a large black buffalo. For theft violations, the perpetrator must "*kuliling lan kampong na megora pentallun kua aku taboko*", or walk around the customary area and admit their mistake three times. This gradation of sanctions demonstrates a proportional and rational customary legal communication system, in which punishment is adjusted to the level of ecological and social damage caused.

This system of sanctions functions as *deterrent* communication, sending a clear message about the consequences of violating environmental norms. Public sanctions, such as walking around the village while admitting guilt, create a strong *shame mechanism* in communal cultures, while also serving as social education for other community members. Economic sanctions, such as slaughtering a large black buffalo for serious violations, not only impose a financial burden on the perpetrator but also have a restorative dimension in which the slaughtered buffalo is distributed to the community as a form of social compensation. Thus, the customary sanction system is not merely punitive but also educational, restorative, and strengthens community solidarity in preserving the forest.

3. Customary Communication Systems in Preserving Ecosystem Sustainability

a. Participatory Communication in Decision Making

Decision-making in the Marena indigenous community is carried out through the "*si ottoman upa*" system, which literally means sitting together with knees touching. Pieter Kadang explains that when indigenous communities gather and talk, they apply a principle called "*si ottoman upa*" or "*cadokko sikumpulu*," where everyone gathers with their knees touching as a symbol of equality and closeness. In these deliberations, the principle of "*Cidokko pada majiong mengke'de pada jao liu*" applies, which means sitting equally low and standing equally high, where all participants have equal rights and

leaders are only given precedence as a sign of respect, not as absolute rulers. This system reflects democratic and inclusive participatory communication, where every member of the community has the same opportunity to express their opinions and contribute to decision-making concerning collective interests.

This participatory decision-making model is in line with the concept of modern environmental communication, which emphasises the importance of stakeholder involvement in natural resource management. (Cox, 2013). The difference lies in the cultural basis that has been deeply rooted for hundreds of years, making participation not just a formal procedure but a value that is practised in everyday life. The "*si ottoman upa*" system also functions as a conflict resolution mechanism, where differences of opinion are resolved through open dialogue and consensus, rather than through voting or unilateral decisions. This creates a sense of *collective ownership* of the decisions made, making their implementation more effective because they are supported by strong social legitimacy.

b. Participatory Monitoring and Surveillance System

Kasim, Secretary of Marena Customary Law and Head of Marena Customary Forest Management, explained that in order to maintain the security of customary forests, the community has individuals who are specifically assigned to inspect and monitor customary forest areas, commonly referred to as "forest police." This traditional monitoring system differs from formal top-down monitoring models. Traditional forest police are members of the community who are trusted by the community to carry out monitoring functions, so that surveillance is not perceived as external pressure but as a form of internal community concern. They patrol regularly, report suspicious activities, and provide early warnings of potential violations or threats to forest sustainability.

The effectiveness of this participatory monitoring system lies in its deep local knowledge of forest conditions, access routes, and community activity patterns. Traditional forest police know every member of the community, understand their needs, and can distinguish between legitimate use and excessive exploitation. This system is also more cost-effective because it does not require enormous operational costs like formal surveillance systems, and is more sustainable because it is based on social commitment rather than purely economic incentives. The existence of traditional forest police creates social surveillance that makes every member of the community feel monitored, but not in a repressive context, instead in a context of solidarity for the common good.

c. Educational Communication and Knowledge Transfer

Pieter Kadang explains that indigenous communities have specific times to gather to socialise with the community about how to preserve the environment and indigenous forests so that customary laws remain in force. This community-based socialisation system is a form of educational communication that is not formal and instructive, but dialogical and contextual. Knowledge about forest management is not conveyed through lectures or formal training, but through casual conversations in customary forums, shared rituals, and mutual assistance activities. This approach allows knowledge to be absorbed naturally and internalised as part of cultural identity, rather than simply cognitive information that is easily forgotten.

Intergenerational knowledge transfer is key to the sustainability of the traditional communication system. Henriyani, Head of the Marena Village Administration, emphasised that since the establishment of traditional institutions and rules, the community has participated in maintaining them so that they can be passed down to their children. This transfer process occurs through various mechanisms, ranging from storytelling about the history of the forest and ancestors, children's participation in traditional rituals, to the direct involvement of the younger generation in forest management activities. This *experiential learning* method is more effective in instilling conservation values than formal education, which is separated from the context of everyday life. The younger generation not only learns about traditional rules but also understands the ecological rationale behind them and directly experiences the benefits of forest conservation for their lives.

d. Sustainable Economic Communication

Kasim explained that the community very much needs customary forests because they are a place to take bamboo to make fences, make ladders to harvest cloves, make paths for tomato plants, wood for cooking, and honey that is sold and used as medicine when sick. This statement shows that communication about forest use is not exploitative but is based on the principles of real needs and sustainability. The community utilises forest products not for capital accumulation but to meet subsistence needs and maintain their traditional agricultural system. This understanding of the multidimensional economic function of forests is communicated intergenerationally, creating awareness that forest conservation is a long-term economic guarantee for the community.

The replacement system in timber utilisation demonstrates concrete sustainable management practices. Kasim explains that if a tree falls and a community wants it, then that community must replace it with two new seedlings of different species, which are then replanted. This system reflects economic communication that focuses not only on extraction but also on regeneration. The obligation to plant two seedlings to replace one tree ensures that the tree stock does not decrease but instead increases over time. The selection of different tree species also demonstrates an understanding of the importance of species diversification to maintain ecosystem resilience. This practice is a concrete manifestation of the principle of "*Mesa soe Mesa Tengka*," whereby current economic benefits must be balanced with ecological responsibility for future generations.

4. Challenges of Modernisation and Communication Adaptation

Pieter Kadang expressed concern about the changes brought about by the introduction of technology, which has slowly eroded the customs they have held for so long. He stated that the nature of the Marena indigenous community is embedded in their hearts, that all people must respect, remind, appreciate, and help one another because these are virtues that have been passed down from generation to generation. Cultural erosion due to modernisation is a serious challenge to the sustainability of the traditional communication system. The younger generation, exposed to social media, urban lifestyles, and individualistic values, tends to lose its emotional connection to the forest and ancestral traditions. Traditional oral and ritualistic communication competes with instant and visual digital communication, creating an intergenerational gap in the transmission of local knowledge.

However, the Marena Indigenous community has also demonstrated its ability to adapt in the face of modernisation challenges. Pieter Kadang explained that recently, the government distributed coffee seedlings to the Marena Indigenous community to be planted in their gardens or customary forests, with the harvest to be shared. Collaboration with the government and the integration of modern economic commodities such as coffee into the customary forest management system demonstrate a smart adaptation strategy. The community does not reject modernisation entirely, but integrates it with traditional values. Planting coffee in customary forests with a profit-sharing system is a form of agroforestry that not only provides economic benefits but also encourages the younger generation to remain involved in forest management due to economic incentives. This strategy shows that customary communication is not static but dynamic, capable of negotiating change while maintaining the essence of conservation values.

5. Effectiveness of Indigenous Communication Systems in Forest Conservation

The local wisdom-based environmental communication system in the Marena Customary Forest has proven highly effective in maintaining ecosystem sustainability through the holistic integration of rituals, norms, and sanctions that reinforce each other. These three elements do not stand alone but form a comprehensive system. Rituals provide spiritual legitimacy, norms provide behavioural guidelines, and sanctions provide real consequences for violations. All three are communicated consistently through various channels, both formal (customary deliberations) and informal (daily interactions), creating message saturation that ensures every community member understands and internalises conservation values.

The community's active participation in the monitoring and decision-making system creates a sense of collective ownership of the customary forest. Unlike top-down conservation models, which often encounter local resistance, the Marena customary communication system is based on consensus and the active involvement of all community members. Each person is not only an object of the rules but also a subject responsible for enforcing them. The "*si ottoman upa*" system ensures that important decisions about forest management are made collectively. In contrast, the "forest police" system ensures that monitoring is carried out by people trusted by the community itself, not by external parties who do not understand the local context.

Intergenerational knowledge transfer ensures the long-term sustainability of conservation traditions. The Marena traditional communication system does not rely on written documentation or formal institutions to maintain knowledge continuity, but on oral transmission, ritual practices, and experience-based learning. Although this method may seem fragile in the face of modernisation, it has proven effective for hundreds of years because knowledge is not only stored in the form of cognitive information but also in the form of social practices embedded in everyday life. Each generation not only inherits knowledge but also modifies and adapts it according to the challenges of their time, making the indigenous communication system a living tradition that continues to evolve.

Adapting to modern challenges while maintaining core values demonstrates the resilience of the indigenous communication system. The Marena Indigenous People are not rigid in the face of change, but selective in adopting elements of modernity that are compatible with their traditional values. Collaboration with the government on coffee seedling programs, openness to technology for documentation and external

communication, and willingness to interact with researchers and environmental activists show that the indigenous communication system is capable of evolving without losing its identity. The success of this system lies in its ability to integrate spiritual, social, and ecological aspects into a comprehensive communication framework, making the Marena Indigenous community a model of sustainable forest management based on local wisdom that is relevant not only to the local context but also as inspiration for alternative conservation models at the global level.

CONCLUSION

This study reveals that the local wisdom-based environmental communication system in the Marena Customary Forest, Enrekang Regency, is a comprehensive and practical model of forest conservation that has survived for hundreds of years. The environmental communication patterns applied by the Marena indigenous community are manifested in three primary forms that are integrated. First, ritual communication through traditional ceremonies such as the manuk-lappa lappa offering at sacred springs before agricultural activities and land clearing procedures involving traditional leaders, which serve as spiritual legitimisation and a social control mechanism for the utilisation of forest resources. Second, normative communication through the customary prohibition system (Eda wa'ding), which includes three basic rules: prohibition of taking wood without permission, prohibition of clearing forests, and prohibition of burning forests, as well as rules of symbolic behaviour in dressing and cooking in sacred areas that strengthen collective awareness of the sacredness of forest areas. Third, sanction communication through a layered traditional punishment system that is proportional to the level of violation, ranging from expulsion from customary areas, cutting off access to water, to the obligation to slaughter a black buffalo for serious violations, which functions as deterrent communication as well as a restorative mechanism to strengthen community solidarity.

The customary communication system, which includes rituals, norms, and traditional sanctions, plays a fundamental role in preserving the Marena Customary Forest ecosystem through several mechanisms. The Sia Nenek customary institutional structure, with four customary leaders (Batu Ariri) without a formal hierarchy, applies the egalitarian principle of "*Mesa soe Mesa Tengka Pada Tallan Pada Lindang*," which creates a participatory decision-making system through "si ottoman upa" (sitting together with knees touching), ensuring that every community member has an equal opportunity to contribute to forest management. The monitoring system through traditional "forest police," who are members of the community themselves, creates effective but non-repressive social surveillance, based on community trust and deep local knowledge of forest conditions. Educational communication through community-based socialisation and intergenerational knowledge transfer ensures that conservation values are internalised as cultural identity and transmitted sustainably to younger generations through *storytelling*, participation in rituals, and experiential learning. Sustainable economic practices with a replacement system (planting two seedlings for every tree taken) demonstrate the integration of economic dimensions with ecological responsibility, ensuring forest regeneration while meeting the subsistence needs of the community.

The success of the local wisdom-based environmental communication system in the Marena Customary Forest lies in its ability to integrate spiritual, social, and ecological aspects into a holistic and comprehensive communication framework. Rituals provide

transcendent legitimacy that connects conservation practices with the dimension of belief in ancestors and God, norms provide concrete guidance on permissible and prohibited behaviours, sanctions provide proportional real consequences, while participatory systems ensure democratic and inclusive implementation. Despite facing the challenges of modernisation in the form of cultural erosion due to technological penetration and shifting values among the younger generation, the Marena Indigenous community has shown resilience through selective adaptation strategies by integrating compatible elements of modernity, such as collaboration with the government on coffee seedling and agroforestry programs, without sacrificing the essence of their traditional values. The Marena communication model offers a preservation framework that is resistant to changing times because it is based on communal values embedded in everyday life, rather than on formal regulations that are easily ignored when oversight weakens.

This research contributes theoretically by enriching the environmental communication literature through an in-depth exploration of how traditional communication systems based on local wisdom function as effective conservation instruments, complementing the dominance of modern environmental communication perspectives that tend to ignore spiritual and cultural dimensions in natural resource management. Practically, the findings of this study show that a community-based conservation approach that respects local knowledge systems and customary institutional structures can be a more sustainable alternative to *top-down* conservation models, which often fail due to local resistance and a lack of community ownership.

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